

HYBRID CONDUCTIVE POLYMER COMPOSITES: THE EFFECT OF MIXED FILLERS AND POLYMER BLENDS ON PYRORESISTIVE PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

High density polyethylene (HDPE) filled with silver coated glass fillers prepared via melt extrusion is used as a reference in this study. The effect of both the addition of second filler (eg CNT) and a second polymer (thermoplastic elastomer) to the reference composite were examined. The addition of the secondary filler promoted the reduction of the percolation threshold of the composite forming hybrid conductive pathways. The PTC intensity of the composite was also improved by the addition of the secondary filler and an increase in the secondary filler increased the PTC intensity and reduced the electrical percolation. Addition of small amount of thermoplastic elastomer not only enhanced the PTC effect but it also improved substantially the flexibility of the composite. SEM images in Fig 3 showed that the interpenetrated morphology of the blend. With conductive fillers selectively dispersed in the HDPE phase.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conductive polymer composites (CPC) are composites made up of an insulating polymer matrix and a conductive filler such as carbon nanotubes, carbon black or metallic powders [1-3]. The sudden change in resistivity of some CPCs within a narrow range of temperature known as the positive temperature coefficient (PTC) effect makes CPCs very attractive in applications such as self regulated heaters and over current protectors. Different theories are proposed for the origin of the PTC effect [4, 5] but the relatively large specific volume change of the polymer matrix close to its melting temperature is seen as the main cause.

One problem associated with CPCs is the decrease in resistivity after the PTC effect known as the negative temperature coefficient (NTC) effect. This makes most CPCs unsuitable for many

applications such as self regulated heaters. The NTC effect is caused by the reagglomeration of the conductive fillers after the melting of polymer matrix [6].

An increase in positive temperature coefficient (PTC) intensity and elimination of the negative temperature coefficient (NTC) effect are important in applications employing conductive polymer composites (CPC) such as self regulated heaters. Several researchers have used different methods such as crosslinking the polymer using irradiation or mechanical stretching to improve the PTC behaviour of the composite and reducing the NTC effect [7-10]. Crosslinking the polymer by irradiation is expensive and also provides problems with recycling. The use of a polymer with high viscosity as a secondary polymer can help reduce or eliminate the NTC effect with the high viscosity polymer constraining the filler movement but commercial processing methods aren't suitable for these kinds of polymers [6, 11, 12]. Many researchers [11, 13-16] have succeeded in using a combination of two polymers to enhance the PTC effect and reduce the percolation threshold of conductive composites. The conductive fillers can be segregated in one polymer phase or at the interface between the two polymers. The segregation of the conductive fillers leads to low percolation thresholds and enhanced PTC effect [11, 17].

The properties of the conductive filler used in the preparation of the composite can be used to improve the sudden jump in resistivity with increase in temperature (PTC effect). The shape and size of the filler is crucial in the electrical and PTC behaviour of the composite. Luo and Wong demonstrated that the PTC intensity of a composite can be increased by using large conductive particles [18]. They argued that conductive particles with bigger particle size, small surface area and small amounts of clusters form weaker conductive paths therefore they are easier to disturb hence the increase in PTC intensity. The problem with this approach is that bigger conductive fillers are also associated with high percolation threshold (i.e. the minimum amount of conductive particles needed to make the insulating polymer become conductive) due to the increase in inter-particle distance [18, 19]. According to Jing *et al.* [19] the diameter of the conductive particle is directly proportional to the percolation threshold so an increase in particle size of the conductive filler will increase the room temperature resistivity of the composite.

High aspect ratio conductive fillers such as multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) have been used to reduce the percolation threshold of conductive polymer composites [20-24]. Carbon black which is assumed to be spherical has a low aspect ratio compared to MWCNT and composites based on carbon black has a higher PTC intensity than composites of the same polymer that employed MWCNT [25-28]. Due to the high resistivity at room temperature of carbon black based composites, high aspect ratio fillers such as MWCNT have been utilised in carbon black based composites in order to reduce the room temperature resistivity [20, 29-31].

Flexible CPCs with high PTC intensities are desirable in many self regulating heaters across a broad range of industries. In this study two strategies are pursued to fulfil the above requirements; hybrid fillers to overcome the compromise between PTC intensity and percolation threshold and elastomeric polymer blending to enhance mechanical flexibility.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

High density polyethylene (HDPE) (MF1: 18g/10mins 2.16 kg load, density: 952 kg/m³), obtained from Ineos Polyolefins under the trade name Rigidex HD5218EA. For the mixed (hybrid) polymer composites, the second polymer is a plastomer based on propylene-ethylene copolymer (Versify) produced by Dow. Silver coated glass flakes (AgF) of different sizes (small and big) were procured from Glassflake Ltd and Nippon Sheet Glass. The properties of the glass based conductive fillers are presented in the table below.

Particle	Size/ μm	Silver content / %wt	Thickness/ μm
AgF_S	5	10-13	0.8-1.2
AgF_L	100	15-36.5	1.0-1.3

Table 1 Properties of the conductive fillers as supplied by the manufacturer

The composites were prepared via a melt extrusion method using a mini extruder with screw speed 50 rpm, processing temperature of 170°C and a residing time of 15 minutes. The extruded strands were pelletized and hot pressed into rectangular shapes ((25mm × 4mm × 2mm) and hot press for 3 minutes using a pressure of 60 bars after holding it at a temperature of 200°C for 5 minutes. Brass electrodes were attached to the ends of the sample after silver paste was coated at the ends to reduce the contact resistance between the electrode and the sample. The sample was heated and the thermo-resistive behaviour studied.

The morphology of the samples was studied by FEI Inspect-F scanning electron microscope (SEM) after fracturing it in liquid nitrogen.

Thermal analysis on the samples was performed using a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (Mettler Toledo DSC-882). Thermal analysis was performed in a nitrogen environment and the sample was heated from room temperature to 250°C at a heat rate of 10°C/min and then cooled back to room temperature at the same rate. The second heating curve is used in examining the thermal behaviour of the composite.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. PTC effect of AgF_S/AgF_L/HDPE and PPE/HDPE/AgF_S

The addition of silver coated large glass flakes (AgF_L) to AgF_S/HDPE composite reduced the amount of AgF_S needed to make the composite conductive as shown in figure 1a. An increase in AgF_L increases the room temperature conductivity of the composite. This might have been caused by the two particles forming a hybrid conductive network. The distance between two or more AgF_S particles might be connected by AgF_L particles to form a conductive pathway as proposed by Dang *et al* [29].

Figure 1 a) Electrical behaviour and b) PTC intensity of HDPE/AgFS and HDPE/AgFS/AgF_L

The PTC Intensity (PTC_1) defined as the ratio of the logarithm of maximum resistivity ($\text{Log } \rho_{\text{max}}$) of the composite to the logarithm of the resistivity at room temperature ($\text{Log } \rho_r$) (i.e $PTC_1 = \text{Log } \rho_{\text{max}} /$

$\log \rho_{rt}$) can be used to investigate the PTC effect. The PTC intensity which is an indicator of the PTC effect decreased with decreasing filler concentration due to the reduction in conductive pathway. Addition of large silver coated flakes (AgF_L) increased the PTC intensity of the AgF_S/HDPE composite. An increase in the concentration of AgF_L increased the PTC intensity and this might have been caused by the increase in participation of AgF_L in the formation of conductive pathways. As the particle size increases the PTC intensity increases due to the reduction in surface area of the particles. A decrease in inter-particle interactions increases the ease with which the conductive pathways can be disrupted.

It was observed that the hybrid composite ($\text{PPE}/\text{HDPE}/\text{AgF}_S$) did not exhibit the classical double positive temperature coefficient (PTC) effect reported in literature. The PTC effect happened close to the melting temperature of HDPE. The increase in resistivity of the composite around the melting point of the HDPE might have been caused by the melting of the crystallites in the HDPE. The increase in resistivity with temperature was immediately followed by a decrease in resistivity also known as the negative temperature coefficient (NTC) effect for both hybrid composites. This was caused by the reagglomeration of the conductive fillers [6]. The PTC intensity increased with increasing elastomer content as observed in figure 2a.

Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) was used to investigate the effect of crystallinity on the PTC intensity. The crystallinity of the composite seems to reduce from 53.09% for the HDPE/AgF_S to 48.51% for 20%wt $\text{PPE}/\text{HDPE}/\text{AgF}_S$. This shows that the crystallinity of the composite was not affected much by the addition of the PPE polymer. Figure 2b shows the DSC curve for the HDPE/AgF_S and hybrid composite and no obvious peak was observed for the elastomer in the hybrid composite. The DSC curve also shows that the PTC effect occurred close to the melting point of HDPE.

Figure 2 PTC intensity and DSC curve for the polymer composites

B. Morphology of $\text{AgF}_S/\text{AgF}_L/\text{HDPE}$ and $\text{PPE}/\text{HDPE}/\text{AgF}_S$

The structure of the conductive polymer composites were investigated using scanning electron microscopy after fracturing in liquid nitrogen. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of high density polyethylene (HDPE) filled with hybrid silver coated glass flakes (AgF) and the hybrid polymer is shown in figure 2. It can be observed that both images show well dispersed fillers in HDPE matrix. The conductive fillers in both composites were randomly orientations within the polymer matrix. Different particle sizes and shapes were observed for the silver flakes.

The SEM micrograph (Fig3a) shows a segregated structure with silver flakes dispersed in the HDPE phase. Dispersing the silver coated glass flakes in the HDPE first before further mixing with the elastomer might have helped the fillers to remain in the HDPE phase. The high viscosity of the elastomer compared to the HDPE might have also played a part in the fillers not migrating into the

plastomer. It was observed that the conductive particles in the composites were at an angle to the fractured surface but some particles were observed to have not been embedded in the polymer matrix.

Figure 3 SEM micrographs of a) HDPE/AgF and b) hybrid polymer filled with AgF

4. CONCLUSION

High density polyethylene (HDPE) filled with silver coated glass flakes (5µm) was investigated and the effect on PTC by addition of a second filler (100µm silver coated glass flake) or matrix (polypropylene elastomer) to the composite were examined. The addition of the secondary filler promoted an increase in electrical properties and PTC intensity with an increase in secondary filler increasing the PTC intensity of the composite. The bigger flakes acted like a bridge between the small flakes and this helped to enhance the electrical properties. The PTC behaviour of the composite was also improved by the addition of the bigger flakes due to the increase in separation distance between particles caused by the bigger flakes. Although there was an increase in PTC intensity of the composite, the PTC behaviour of the composites was dominated by the primary filler.

Adding a polypropylene ethylene based plastomer to the composite also increased the PTC intensity. Selective dispersion of fillers in HDPE was achieved.

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